

THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF TEACHER EDUCATION STUDENTS ENROLLED IN A STUDENT-CENTERED ENVIRONMENT: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

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The Lived Experiences of Teacher Education Students Enrolled in a Student-Centered Environment: A Phenomenological Study

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Abstract

The research investigates the lived experience of teacher education students enrolled in a student-centered classroom environment. A classroom environment plays a vital role in developing academic performance through differentiated learning experiences. In the Philippine higher education under the implementation of a new curriculum, a focus on student-centered teaching approach was highlighted to achieve the goals of outcome-based education. The study about the students' lived experiences in a student-centered classroom setting could determine the strengths and weaknesses of the teaching methodology. In achieving the research objectives, the researchers conducted a series of classroom observations to observe the student's behavior in a student-centered approach. In the latter part of the semester, an interview among the enrolled students was conducted. The study is a qualitative method using the phenomenological approach wherein the lived experiences of the students are documented and analyzed. The findings revealed that interpersonal skills, creativity, and self-esteem were aspects of personality that were improved in a student-centered classroom environment. This reveals that the current trend in teaching approach contributes not only to the academic achievement of the students but also to their personal development.

Keywords: *professional education, teaching and learning, 21st century education, student-centered learning*

Introduction

A student-centered environment plays a vital role in enhancing learning experiences and academic growth (Wulf, 2019; Villarroel et al., 2020). The student-centered environment aims to develop sense of responsibility, autonomy, and self-reflection towards lifelong learning of the students (El Hammoumi et al., 2020). It certainly asserts that this form of teaching will always result in an output that practices the learned theories that a student learned during a predetermined period (Tadesse, 2020).

Student-centered teaching approach made its way to the teacher education curriculum, introducing the use of technology and innovation of teaching strategies in training students to become productive teachers (Chakrabarty, 2020). The teacher education program's primary direction is on preparing students to become teachers and the quality of teaching approaches that rely on the student's abilities and skills (Soh, 2020). Using the teaching strategies that shape the student's minds and activity within the classroom, teachers can successfully reassure the student's self-regulation in a student-centered environment (Aslam et al., 2021)

The shift from traditional pedagogy came when the concept of outcomes-based education was introduced. Outcomes-based education has been a primary direction in educational reform in the United States as the students prefer to develop their practical skills more rather than theoretical knowledge as the former makes it more plausible for their future employment (Asim et al., 2021). In the Philippines, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) implemented Outcome-Based Education (OBE) after the release of Executive Order No. 83, s. 2012 on the Institutionalization of the Philippine Qualifications Framework (PQF). Its primary purpose is to formulate and recommend development plans, policies, and programs for tertiary education (Fernando, 2021). This is formulated to set the standards that an individual needs to possess to have a better career and develop into a self-sufficient individual. These qualifications are essential to the students for them to accurately attain the skills needed for the real world and make themselves productive and effective individuals.

Fatima (2020) stated that to attain the set standards, students should be allowed to participate in planning, diagnosing needs, and setting of learning goals to make sure that the ownership of learning is truly emphasized. In a student-centered learning approach, the student should not be the recipient of the information, but an active participant in the teaching and learning process (El Hammoumi et al., 2020). Therefore, a student-centered approach makes the students participate in the teaching and learning process and shifts the teacher's role from being the source of information to being the facilitator of knowledge (Fernando, 2021).

Teachers' classroom management skills are considered one of the most important elements that teachers should have to create an effective education and training environment (Bozkuş, 2021). An effective student-centered environment can be dependent on the teacher's classroom management skills (Wulf, 2019). It requires the skills that can address the abnormal and disruptive behaviors that can delay the teaching and learning process. There are differences observed from both teacher-centered and student-centered approaches. Collaboration between the teacher and the students is very limited in the teacher-centered environment, leading to independence and isolation between one another (Bilbao et al., 2020a, p. 161). On the other hand, a student-centered environment suggests that teachers and students work in teams, improving collaboration skills (Bilbao et al., 2020b, p. 161).

A student-centered teaching approach is widely implemented in higher education institutions in compliance with the goals of outcomes-based education. However, the effectiveness of this approach in teacher education still needs more studying. Therefore, active

learning/student-centered approaches such as the inquiry method, problem solving, and discovery methods that foster the critical thinking and problem-solving capacity of students were not widely employed (Takele, 2020), further questioning the effectiveness of this approach to the students. Therefore, further measuring its effectiveness, the basic aim of this study is to present the lived experiences of students enrolled in the course “Facilitating Learner-Centered Teaching” under the Department of Teacher Education of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College and how their instructors handle a student-centered environment. Moreover, this also aims to determine what skills should be developed when innovating teaching strategies to fully maximize the use of a student-centered classroom.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the lived experiences of teacher education students enrolled in a student-centered environment and its effects on the teaching and learning process. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the opportunities that teacher education students gain in a student-centered classroom?
2. What are the challenges being faced by teacher education students in a student-centered environment to the teaching and learning process?
3. What skills should be developed that can be considered in creating teaching strategies appropriate in a student-centered classroom?

Literature Review

Traditional classroom culture is grounded upon the concept that the teacher is the most important stakeholder in the teaching and learning process by virtue of her/his “knowledge” (Arman, 2018). In a traditional classroom setting, where the teacher is the source of knowledge and the student is the audience, collaboration between the students and the teacher is limited in terms of participation in the class (Bilbao et al., 2020, p. 161). For example, the study of Kilic (2023) stated that the teacher-centered language teaching technique arranges lessons in a preset, linear pattern, frequently based on a certain textbook or curriculum. The linear approach in a teacher-centered classroom can be time-consuming, and it can produce stress for both the student and the teacher, with more stringent deadlines on activities and more exhaustive learning habits (Benlahcene et al., 2020).

The competencies of the students are acquired through formal education; which is crucial to their future success and satisfaction in life (Custodio et al., 2019). These shifts in notions of the 21st-century learner have also led to changes in how society views the student, who now emerges as an autonomous and self-determining individual (Hirschman & Wood, 2018). Therefore, 21st-century learners have self-awareness that may lead them to succeed in choosing their career path to create the future they want to build rather than on what society says about how they should build their own career (Dariyono & Rusman, 2023). In recent times, 21st-century competencies have made a significant shift in pedagogy from previous practices and encourage students to follow the skills and competencies that are necessary for their survival and development (Hemmati & Azizmalayeri, 2022). Competencies in the 21st century were fundamental for students to develop to be globally competitive and self-sufficient to become better individuals.

In a student-centered classroom, the teacher’s role should be portrayed as the facilitator, who guides and supports students in their academic journey rather than being the sole source of information (Komalasari & Puspitasari, 2023). The core concept of the student-centered environment is that the teacher can help the students learn by employing teaching strategies that both lengthen the attention span of the students and make learning fun. El Hammoumi et al., (2020) emphasized that the teacher’s role in the teaching and learning process in modern times should be that of a helper, a planner, a guide, and a shaper of the student’s achievements. The shift to the student-centered learning approach retains the “control” of the teacher in the teaching and learning process, using the pedagogically appropriate methods that help the students learn effectively (Tadesse, 2020). Without those roles, the teaching and learning process is strained and limits the output being achieved by the students (Bilbao et al., 2020, p. 161).

On the other hand, the role of the students is to actively participate in finding solutions to the questions posed in the learning process (Sanchez et al., 2023). Consequently, the active participation of the students makes a significant contribution to the teaching and learning process since it is the students who are in the spotlight in the student-centered environment (El Hammoumi et al., 2020). The role of the students in a student-centered environment is learning by doing (Takele, 2020). Students participate in activities that simulate real-world roles and professions while learning the topic that is discussed.

Higher education globally has faced major changes over the years, shifting from the traditional curriculum that was subject-centered, teacher-oriented, and didactic towards a curriculum that is learner-centered, learner-oriented, flexible, interactive, integrated, competency-based, outcome-based, and gives ownership of learning to the students (Khanna & Mehrotra, 2019). Since the world is already in the 21st century, the approach of teaching has already transformed from traditional to online classes. On the other hand, these sources of outcomes include regulatory bodies, institutional philosophy, industry demands, subject matter experts, curriculum benchmarks, and learning frameworks (Cahapay, 2021). It emerged in the result that multiple sources were considered in making decisions about the outcomes.

Under the guidance of outcomes-based education, the student-centered approach focuses on students’ learning objectives and outcomes, and the students play the roles and teachers act as coaches in a classroom environment (Zhang & Ge, 2022). The new implementing teaching approach in the 21st century, where it was designed to focus on student development (student-centered) rather than teacher-

centered. Damit et al. (2021) stated that this type of arrangement has transformed the conventional education system into a new and more student-centered approach, where students can learn the specific subject in their ways.

The student-centered approach aims to help students develop a sense of responsibility and autonomy in learning. It replaces the old notion of schooling in which the teacher is the sole source of information, while the students are the audience. There are factors which affect how teaching strategies should be used appropriately in the teaching and learning process. The roles of the teachers and the students are shifted the same as the paradigm shift in teaching. Teachers have shifted their roles from being the only source of information to being the facilitators of the learning process. The students, on the other hand, became active participants in the learning process because they were now responsible for their learning. Therefore, a student-centered approach helps the students discover their skills and enhance their potential with the guidance of the teachers, enabling them to be productive professionals in the future.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative method engaging specifically to a phenomenological approach to understand the lived experiences of teacher education students enrolled in a student-centered environment. A phenomenological design was used to identify the phenomena, focus on the subjective experiences of the participants, and understand the structure of the lived experiences of the participants. Using this approach, the researchers discovered the opportunities and challenges of a student-centered learning environment and the skills that should be developed in innovating teaching strategies appropriate in a student-centered classroom

Participants

The participants of this study were chosen using the purposive sampling technique among the teacher education students who enrolled in Facilitating Learner-Centered Teaching wherein a student-centered environment was implemented. The following are the criteria in selecting the participants; (a) a teacher education student; (b) currently enrolled in the course “Facilitating Learner-Centered Teaching” A.Y. 2023-2024; and (c) availability and willingness to participate in the study. There was a total of 14 students enrolled in the course but only 12 students participated in the study.

Instruments

The researchers prepared interview questions that would achieve the objectives of the study. The set of the questionnaire was organized based on the research objectives. The questionnaire consisted of eight (8) questions that focused on the following: (1) the opportunities gained by the students in a student-centered environment, (2) the challenges encountered by the students, and (3) the skills that teachers should consider in innovating activities in a student-centered environment. To analyze the answers of the respondents, a thematic interpretation was employed.

Procedure

The researchers conducted this study as one of the requirements of teaching internship. The researchers were guided by a research adviser from topic selection to title construction and up to the content validation and proofreading of this study. Numerous consultations were made to make necessary revisions and additions for the improvement and credibility of this study. A research proposal was presented to a panel before the start of this study. Since the research adviser is an expert in a student-centered approach, therefore, the class that the research adviser is handling was chosen to be observed and interviewed. The researchers conducted several classroom observations to gain knowledge and witness how the student-centered approach is being done inside the classroom and how teacher education students can apply this approach once they are in the field of teaching. A few weeks before the end of the semester, an interview was conducted. The research adviser taught the researchers how to interpret the interview using thematic analysis and interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers, understanding the ethics and principles of responsible research writing, expressed their intent to conduct this study with a letter proposal. The research adviser provides a proper procedure on how to conduct the research in compliance with the guidelines. Prior to the interview to know the lived experiences of the participants, the researchers sought approval of the study from the professor who facilitated the course. Participants of the interview permitted the researchers to record the conversation that would later be transcribed for interpretation. The researchers ensured that there is no plagiarized content in this study through a plagiarism checker.

Results and Discussion

The analysis was done by reading through all responses given by the participants and analyzing each by clustering to different themes. No application was used during the analysis.

Metaphors for Student-Centered Learning

Participants D and I's metaphor for student-centered learning are learning materials. It was emphasized that students were able to

interact with those materials, therefore enhancing learning by doing. Another metaphor mentioned by some of the participants is a GPS, a navigation material. The responses emphasized the students' exploration on their journey to knowledge with the teacher as their guide by giving them creative and innovative activities for the learners to choose from to exert their best effort in making sure that their output is executed flawlessly. In contrast, the metaphor given by Participant B is an explorer. The participant's answer focused on the vast learning environment a student will go on their journey for learning.

The words facilitator and classroom were also provided as a metaphor wherein they see that student-centered learning is always facilitated by the teacher. It gives importance to the students having the ability to add information to the topic discussed. Additionally, Participant F's metaphor is games and activities that can make student-centered learning fun and interactive. In addition, a participant views the subject as a garden, focusing on the part that students have multiple intelligences. Thus, a teacher can make innovations to tap into each student's potential. Additionally, another participant's metaphor is a ballpen, focusing on the student's use of learning as their building blocks to attain their future career. Lastly, a learning strategy as a metaphor that emphasizes participation and collaboration between students was also provided.

Most of the metaphors provide emphasis on the benefits of the student-centered learning on the side of the student. It emphasizes the things a student can earn from the innovations the teachers do to make learning more fun and interactive. On the other hand, some of the metaphors provided were focused on the teaching-learning relationship that forms in a student-centered classroom. It pertains to the teacher facilitating learning while the students will give information on a certain topic.

Positive Impact of Student-Centered Learning on Classroom Performance

Participants have given multiple responses on how student-centered learning has a positive impact on their classroom performance. They expressed that student-centered learning improved collaboration. The participants emphasized that student-centered learning is collaborative in nature and enhances the quality of work when students work together as a group. Additionally, participants emphasized the impact of student-centered learning in terms of positive classroom management. They also emphasized that having a positive classroom culture has a positive effect on student learning. In addition, there are participants who stated that interactivity in the classroom is one of the positive impacts of student-centered learning. It can also enhance socialization skills as they share their ideas and thoughts about the topic discussed during the class.

Participant J said that student-centered learning enhanced their critical thinking skills. He emphasized that student-centered learning makes the students think deeply as they learn more things. Participants D and H said that student-centered learning allowed self-expression and creativity while in class, therefore improving their confidence. A positive school environment also engages the students in expressing what they are using their outputs and performances. On the other hand, Participant K said that student-centered learning enhanced their physical and mental activity. Since skills development is the center of student-centered learning, the emphasis for physical and mental development is manifested as they do simulations and demonstrations.

Common to all the answers denote the positive impacts of student-centered learning in terms of the whole classroom setting. It emphasizes how the class sees the improvement of their skills when they are in a student-centered classroom. On the other hand, there were participants who emphasizes the positive impact of student-centered learning on an individual's perspective.

Challenges Encountered in a Student-Centered Classroom

Participants aired their concerns about the challenges they encountered in a student-centered classroom. Challenges encountered in a student-centered classroom were having difficulties understanding the topic, having difficulty socializing with peers, and having a wide imagination, as mentioned by three participants. They emphasized that in a student-centered classroom, students sometimes have problems understanding the topic due to either time constraints or the quantity of activities being administered that are sometimes not related to the lesson. Also, even though a student-centered classroom improves collaboration skills, there will be instances that due to being shy, students have difficulty socializing with their peers, making the notion that the classroom is a place of competition, not of learning. Another is that having a wide imagination on how they do the activity may also cause difficulties since there will be instances that a student can be a perfectionist and cannot process what output is best to submit.

Another challenge that the participants encountered were difficulties on classroom management, time management, and the diversity of learning styles and needs. Sometimes, poor time management in the classroom deters the effective delivery of the lesson. For example, a teacher may deliver the lesson for two days if poor time management is manifested and cannot deliver it in one day. Also, there will be instances where a teacher misses some learning styles and needs of students. Therefore, it can be a burden to the teacher to adjust the mode of delivery of the lesson and activities to the students. Another concern by the participants is focused on the assessment and evaluation of a student's output. It can also be difficult for the teacher to check how they graded due to the quantity of activities administered to them.

Slow learners and student's motivation are challenges in a student-centered classroom setup according to another participant. Sometimes, it can be problematic since students have their own pace on how fast they can learn something. Motivation of the students can decrease overtime since students nowadays have limited learning span. Participant C only expresses his challenge as some teachers misinterpreted the meaning of student-centered learning as administering as many classroom activities to students. Alternatively, a

participant's challenge is the culture shock when he is in a student-centered classroom. This emphasis is made on the fact that some students have little to no knowledge on the concept of the student-centered setup.

One participant's concern is the activities and the execution of the lesson. Sometimes, the execution of the lesson in a student-centered classroom is misinterpreted as more activities and less discussion, which is detrimental to the students' knowledge rather than beneficial. In addition, one emphasized that there are students who refuse to participate in the activities administered by the teacher. Sometimes, due to them being shy, the activity consumes too much time, therefore impeding the learning process. Finally, Participant L's response was that the students tend to make a lot of noise and cause chaos in the classroom, therefore it delays further with the teacher delivering the lesson to them.

The common response from the participants stated the challenges they see in student-centered learning from the teacher's perspective, since these challenges delay how the lesson is delivered to them. It also affects the teaching-learning process of the students. On the contrary, other common responses from the participants expressed their concerns about the challenges they encountered in the eyes of the students. Since some students have different abilities and learning styles, the teacher can have difficulty innovating and administering activities that suit all learning styles and habits.

Observations on their Professors Handling a Student-Centered Classroom

Four participants revealed that professors act as a facilitator of teaching. Therefore, they use their own approaches in administering their activity and innovating such activities to help the students hone their critical thinking skills (Bilbao et al., 2020, p. 161). On the other hand, they expressed that their professors understand the students' diverse needs and construct different methods and styles. Teachers often seek the student's needs by administering diagnostic examinations and from there, they are innovating activities that seem appropriate to their learning needs (Asim et al, 2021).

Another set of participants said that their professors let them collaborate and perform different tasks by giving them instruction first. Collaboration is one of the appropriate steps in making sure that the students deliver their knowledge on their own with the guidance of their teachers (Bilbao et al, 2020, p. 161; Fatima, 2020). While others expressed that their professors treat this setup as a ground for self-expression and feedback.

The common observation focused on the teaching strategies of their professors and how they deliver their lessons. On the other hand, other answers from the participants were based on their perceptions on the activities administered to them and the type of evaluation they do to assess them.

Aspects of the Student-Centered Program that Improves Personal and Professional Development of Students

Participants have expressed multiple aspects of the student-centered program that improved their personal and professional development. Enhancing their self-confidence during the student-centered program improved their personal development according to the participants. They see that performances in their activities make them confident about themselves and turn them into better individuals (Mallahi, 2022). Moreover, Participant C, F and K states that a student-centered classroom helped them picture a new meaning of teaching, therefore uncovering their hidden skills and abilities. Moreover, they think that it helped them realize that they can do more than their abilities.

Adaptation of method of teaching is an example of a good student-centered program, is one of the common answers given by the participants. They realized that student-centered learning helped them to improve their critical thinking and creative skills. In contrast, Participants B and L revealed that student-centered learning dwells on individual needs and capabilities, therefore pushes them to innovate more activities that fit every student's needs. It is also seen that this methodology of teaching and learning helps them realize that the teacher guides every student differently based on their capabilities (Peterson, 2020). Finally, one thing that Participant G and I revealed is that student-centered learning helps them be actively engaged in activities and improve their relationship with their peers and their teachers.

The student-centered program developed the personality of the participants based on the responses. Factors such as exposure to public speaking and enhancing their confidence play a major role in teaching students to be a better person. In addition, another common answer revealed that student-centered environment improved their professional skills. Some factors such as adaptation of teaching methods, and innovation of activities based on student needs and capabilities play a significant role in making students better teachers.

Contribution of Peer-to-Peer and Student-Teacher Interaction to Learning and Growth

Peer-to-peer interaction helped them adapt ideas and strategies for their learning according to the participants. It was also revealed that it also helped them improve their teaching strategies for their teaching demonstrations. Additionally, peer-to-peer interaction improves their critical thinking by collaborating with their peers in their activities. It helps them to think deeper about how they can perfectly execute that kind of activity. Interaction with peers and teachers inside the classroom also helps to see the bigger picture of teaching. In contrast, other participants revealed how student-teacher interaction helped them to boost their confidence and have a great relationship with them.

Common answers reveal how interactions with their peers and teachers helped them to enhance their creativity and critical thinking

through adapting to the ideas and concepts given by their peers for the betterment of their output. On the other hand, participants also reveal the impact of those interactions on their self-confidence and socialization skills, while giving them the bigger picture on how teaching and learning should look like.

Influence of Student-Centered Learning to the Ability to Adapt to Different Teaching and Learning Styles

Most of the participants expressed that student-centered learning influenced them to adapt to the teaching strategies and administering activities. They also said that it piques their creativity in making activities that fit the different intelligences of children. On the other hand, Participant B and H states that it plays a major role by posturing the mindset of openness and flexibility of learning to students. It makes them learn at their own pace by connecting topics into multiple aspects.

Additionally, student-centered learning increased their interest in learning according to one participant. It also piques their curiosity in what they can improve after their activity. Participant E said that it makes them open to collaboration with their peers. On the contrary, Participant A reveals that student-centered learning influenced his ability to adapt to different teaching and learning styles through differentiated instruction. It also reveals that through different activities, students also enhance their critical thinking.

Influence of student-centered learning environment to their teaching and learning styles in terms of adoption and adaptation of teaching strategies and learning habits is one of the answers that most of the participants gave. One of the most important influences of student-centered pedagogy is focused on the innovation of teaching strategies that helped teachers to teach students with multiple intelligences. Another aspect is that student-centered environment helped the students pique their interest in learning.

Influence of Student-Centered Program to their Passion and Commitment to Teaching

Participants have multiple responses on how the student-centered program encouraged them to continue pursuing their profession. Participants A and F expressed that the program helped them by exposure to different tasks and strategies that can help them improve their teaching. They are also exposed to different activities that made them perfect the art of teaching. In contrast, others believed that the enthusiasm, encouragement, and support of their peers and teachers helped them in what they were pursuing. They also emphasized the value of friendships in improving their learning habits.

Student-centered learning improved their willingness to help others and share their knowledge through this program according to some of the participants. They also said that it influenced them to share the information they gained from their peers. Other participants said that it influenced them by seeing the progress they make and the feedback they gain from them. Finally, Participant L revealed that the student-centered pedagogy helped him understand more the profession and specialization he chose.

Themes Generated from the Results

The theme generated from this study focuses on the skills that should be developed in a student-centered classroom that can be considered in innovating teaching strategies and teaching-learning activities that can be appropriate to the teacher education students enrolled in a student-centered environment.

Figure 1. Skills that should be Developed in a Student-Centered Classroom

The teacher must innovate teaching strategies that can tap into the students’ personal development such as improving self-confidence, creativity, curiosity, and improving relationships. These skills are very important in making the students into better individuals.

Self-confidence in a student-centered environment can be improved by innovating activities that maximize the interests and potentials of the students (Zulkifli, 2019). Students have their own hidden potential and are waiting for something that can release it. By innovating activities that tap into their interests and potential, they can use it for the students to overcome their fears and be confident about themselves. On the other hand, being creative can be a great skill that teachers must teach their students (Tamsah et al., 2021). Activities such as poster making and arts and crafts can be great opportunities to enhance creativity, given that there are still rubrics on what expectations the teacher sets for their output.

Additionally, teachers must improve their art of questioning to pique the student's interest. Students can have their curiosity piqued when the teacher asks the question that relates to the interest of the students or the current trends they know (Peterson, 2020). A student-centered classroom can be a playground for the students to make friends and improve how they manage relationships. Teachers can innovate activities that can help them socialize with one another, and to plant to their minds that they all belong and are united.

Teachers must also create teaching strategies that can help the students enhance their skills under professional development such as innovation, collaboration, adaptation, and critical thinking. Their skills can help them in their profession and improve their work ethics in the future.

A student-centered classroom should improve how students can innovate new things. Therefore, teachers can administer experiments to the students and let them discover new things and observe them to the fullest extent. Another skill that should be developed in a student-centered classroom is collaboration. Students tend to collaborate with their peers, and teachers must see it as an opportunity to teach them new skills that help them in creating new ideas that improve their output.

Another skill that helps the students in the real world is the adaptability of the skills that they learn from their peers and how these skills will be applied to their output (Bradberry & De Maio, 2019). Therefore, teachers must guide the students with techniques that help them with their study habits and learning styles. Finally, a student-centered classroom, even if it is full of activities, still must tap into the students' critical thinking skills. Therefore, teachers must integrate questioning techniques into the discussion to make sure that the students still understand the lesson.

Conclusions

Students have realized that student-centered learning influences their abilities and their self-esteem by exposure to the different activities and teaching styles. This study confirms that teacher education students have different thoughts about their experiences in a student-centered classroom. Some students revealed the positive impacts like improving their confidence and adaptation to teaching and learning styles. This style of learning also introduced new pedagogical frameworks that make everything important about teaching and learning. Moreover, it also influenced their adaptation to different teaching and learning habits as well as their capability to understand different students' needs and abilities and use them to innovate more activities that can best fit for them.

However, some challenges they encountered, such as time constraints, students being shy and refusing to participate in the activities, catering to different intelligences, and problems regarding assessment and evaluation, were observed by the participants. Educational institutions must expose teacher education students to more simulations and demonstrations in using technology in teaching and learning, and adapt to the different techniques in lesson delivery, both offline and online. More knowledge has been transferred from the students to their peers, and teachers must process and simplify it to the point that they can understand it even in the simplest form.

Instruction in the classroom is now centered on the student input rather than to the teacher's authoritative knowledge. Gone are the days of teachers forcing students to write lectures to their notebooks (Fernando, 2021). Students now act as a network through which information is transferred and transformed, and teachers must act as facilitators and compasses for the information to manifest into actual output. The teachers who conducted classes in a student-centered classroom methodology should consider that there are skills that should be developed in designing innovative activities that can tap student's needs and interests. Through these activities, teachers may see a significant improvement in the academic performance of the students and can unlock their full potential in things other than what they are capable of.

The researchers suggested based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were presented: (1) Teachers must expose students to more simulations and demonstrations to help them improve their communication skills and confidence. They must also portray more situations that test the students' ability to innovate more strategies that address those situations. (2) Teachers are recommended to apply student-centered approaches, exploring different methods such as project-based learning and collaborative activities. Meeting individual student needs creates a supportive learning environment and adapts different teaching strategies to promote student engagement and develop essential skills for success in the 21st century. (3) For schools, it is important to consider key areas such as the impact of student-centered learning on school culture, the role of organizational development in supporting student-centered learning, the impact of student-centered learning on student outcomes at the school level, and the perspectives of stakeholders on student-centered learning. (4) School heads must effectively train teachers on how they will deliver an effective student-centered classroom to be able to meet the objectives of Outcome-Based Education.

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